

**ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN MODERN TEACHING OF
SPECIALIZED SUBJECTS IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION**

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Introduction

Remains one of the most urgent issues of today. Creating an innovative educational environment, ensuring its full compliance with international standards is an important factor in successfully socializing our youth to today's rapidly changing social life [1]. The implementation of the "National Personnel Training Program" envisages the improvement of the structure and content of the continuing education system on the basis of modern scientific achievements and social experience. For this, first of all, it is necessary to provide teaching processes in all educational institutions with advanced, scientifically-methodically based modern methodology [2]. It is one of the urgent problems facing the system of renewing the purpose, tasks and content of education for the young generation. Today, we all deeply understood that only young people who have received education on a modern basis, who can compete with their peers in other countries of the world, and who are physically and spiritually fit, will be able to adequately continue the work we have started and raise it to a new level.

The purpose of the national model of personnel training.

Its main components are:

- ✓ Person;
- ✓ State and society;
- ✓ Continuing education;
- ✓ Science;
- ✓ Production.

Creates the necessary conditions for the formation of a creative, socially active, spiritually rich person and the training of highly qualified competitive personnel [3].

A distinctive feature of the national model of personnel training is the introduction of independent nine-year general secondary and three-year secondary special education [4].

Requirements for teaching the subject of vocational education methodology. At present, the methodology of teaching special subjects in higher and educational institutions and HEIs, the use of new pedagogical and information technologies in the teaching process, educational methodical education Several noteworthy works are being carried out on supply problems [5]. In particular, seminars and scientific-practical conferences are being held with the participation of mature specialists and qualified pedagogues from foreign countries in order to improve the system of HEIs and to apply modern pedagogical technologies to their educational process [6].

What is modern education?

Modern education is the newest and most modern version of education taught in schools and educational institutions in the 21st century. Modern education focuses not only on the well-known academic subjects of commerce, science and arts, but also on developing students' critical thinking, life skills, learning, analytical and decision-making skills. Modern education also uses the latest technologies such as mobile applications, audio and video platforms such as YouTube, e-books, movies, etc. to teach students and make the learning process more interesting and fun [7]. We've all been in a teacher-centered classroom, where the teacher comes first and the students sit in a neat order, listen to the lecture, and take notes. This system, to some extent, still formed the main part of our educational system. Schools have relied on it for decades and only recently experienced major changes. Living in the 21st century, technology has become an integral part of our daily life. None of us can deny that this has led to a radical change in our world, and most importantly, in the education system. It discusses how these studies can change the modern education system and traditional teaching methods.

The main goals of modern education:

- ✓ important life skills, critical thinking, decision-making skills and analytical skills in students.
- ✓ students' positive attitudes toward diversity, inclusion, compassion, and responsibility.
- ✓ To create a fun and interesting learning process.
- ✓ Incorporating educational technologies to make the learning environment experiential with a focus on real-life application of concepts.
- ✓ education and training accessible anywhere in the world through physical classrooms or online learning.

✓ the teacher and the student and raising the curiosity of the students, teaching them to inquire and ask questions rather than the passive traditional approach.

Eg: Modern Education in India

✓ originates from the ancient oral education and also from the Gurukul education system which was modified by the British as formal education . Here are the main features of modern education in India:

✓ Modern education in India was introduced by British colonialists in the 1830s and the English language was introduced in India by Lord Thomas Babington Macaulay.

✓ metaphysics and philosophy were previously studied at Nalanda University, the new modern education system brought by the British focused on scientific subjects such as science and mathematics.

✓ After India became free from the British, basic education, especially at the age of 6-14, became compulsory with schools built all over the country.

✓ In the 21st century, India's modern-age education system consists of a new approach to online learning, skill development courses, digital learning platforms, assessment systems, and the use and introduction of learning technologies in classrooms.

Modern Education: Analysis

Includes a variety of teaching and learning methods, including the popular "space learning" where students are encouraged to quickly change activities. This is a training method in which abbreviated educational content is provided with a 10-minute break for physical activity. For example, students are given a 15-minute powerpoint presentation followed by a 10-minute sports session. The purpose of this method is to improve their learning ability. Exercise is said to help brain cells make the connections they need to remember the course. It also has the added benefit of allowing people to relax[8].

and interactive for students with the help of various computer technologies, Internet, projector presentations . It encourages students to deal with the real world, to analyze everything that happens in different areas of life. Students are taken to relevant fields and industries where they witness the practical application of the concepts they have learned in theory. These methods help improve the quality of education and increase student engagement.

Leadership qualities in the field of professional training - the history and development prospects of the field of network knowledge to which the taught subject belongs; - to have an idea about the role and importance of the taught subject in the educational process; - About the Law "On Education"; - About the

goals and tasks defined in the "National Personnel Training Program"; - the curriculum of the taught subject; - the modern scientific and practical achievements of one's own science and related field; - concepts, terms and definitions, laws, principles, methods and methods of the subject being taught ; - scientific-practical creativity methodology;

Pedagogical monitoring technology of educational quality. The technological approach is one of the important directions of methodological research in modern pedagogy , and it defines the necessary stages of knowledge and the sequence of actions performed in the organization of pedagogical processes. Through its tools, the transition from the analysis of the elements of the pedagogical system to the design of processes, their adjustment and management is carried out. In a general sense, technology is considered as a method of organizing activities to achieve a set goal.

Modern lessons are characterized by interdependence of components such as mastering, disaggregation, repetition and reinforcement, acquisition of new educational material and control of previously learned material in connection with its practical application. Students' independent work is organized not only at the stages of repetition and reinforcement, but also during the study of new material, through which there is a strong connection between teaching and learning, between the collective work of the class and the individual (individual) work of the student. will be done. Components of students' research activities are used not only in problem-based lessons, but also in some stages of all types of lessons (combined, control, etc.). Depending on the ways of solving the didactic tasks set forward, some stages of the lesson construction procedure may be reduced and expanded, teaching methods and the tasks and roles of various methods may change. Therefore, the structural structure of the modern lesson is very diverse, reflecting the managerial role of teachers and the uniqueness of organizing students' cognitive activities [9].

The competence of self-improvement of a person is aimed at spiritual, motivational, intellectual and practical self-development, volitional and emotional self-control. The student acquires methods of activity according to his personal interests and capabilities, which helps him to develop personal and professional qualities characteristic of a modern specialist, to form his technical thinking, culture and character. The development of professional competence is creative development, the pedagogue's ability to quickly adapt to and manage changes in the environment, the ability to quickly enter, the social-economic and spiritual development of the process depends on the professional level of the pedagogue.

changes in the modern system force the teacher to improve his qualifications and professional skills, which means he has to increase his methodical competence. The main goal of modern education is to adapt the society, the state, and the individual to modern education, to educate a comprehensively developed person. Pedagogical and technical-technological problem situation in formation of methodical competence of vocational education teacher is recorded as a set of conditions that allow to create pedagogical process. Pedagogical conditions not only create this process, but also determine its current state. The formation of methodological competence of the teacher of vocational education is carried out step by step, through the integration of pedagogical subjects, i.e. didactic synthesis and solving pedagogical and problem-situational tasks in their activities at the level of interdisciplinarity.

Summarizing the article, it should be said that based on the development and demand of science and technology, as well as the current demands of the labor market for personnel, the research on the further improvement of the quality of the education system shows that the gradual abandonment of traditional education and requires a transition to modern education. This article also contains analytical thoughts about approaches to modern education.

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